

EVOLUTION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE NIGERIAN PETROLEUM INDUSTRY'S DOWNSTREAM SECTOR

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Abstract: This article explores the evolution and transformation of Nigeria's petroleum industry's downstream sector from the colonial era to the period after independence. The colonialists controlled the industry until the period of the indigenization policy, when local actors were introduced. The author noted that while the upstream sector has received significant attention from scholars and policymakers, the downstream sector needs to be reported because of its importance to the daily life of the Nigerian citizen. To do this, the researcher draws from various sources, including archival materials, newspaper articles, reports of government commissions, and interviews with stakeholders, to explain the downstream sector's evolution and transformation.

Keywords: Downstream Sector, Governance, Middlemen, Petroleum Industry.

Introduction

This study explores the evolution and development of Nigeria's downstream sector. For this study, the downstream oil and gas production companies are close to the end user or consumer, and operations begin after the production phase and continue to the point of sale. Companies engaged in the downstream process include oil refineries, petroleum product distributors, petrochemical plants, natural gas distributors, and retail outlets. This sector includes those that provide usable products to end users. Companies engage in the marketing and distribution of diesel, natural gas, gasoline, heating oil, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, and propane.

Downstream Sector before Political Independence

The urge to use petrol in Nigeria became eminent with the penetration of the colonialists, who needed to actualize the mandate to evacuate local produce from the hinterland to the coastal region in the early period of colonial enterprise.¹ In the first place, the structure of the colonial system's organization, as it was in India and other British colonies, was designed to fulfill the strategic objective of integrating the local Nigerian economy into the global capitalist system.² Arguably, this explains the colonial authority's massive involvement in the development of transport infrastructure that linked the hitherto isolated hinterland with the coastal regions for easy movement of goods to the industrial hubs of Manchester and Liverpool.³ However, diesel, a petroleum product, served as the only source of energy for the *locomotives* that powered the trains.⁴ Even the automobiles reserved for

¹Syracuse University (Syracuse, NY, USA) Maxwell Graduate School of Citizenship and Public Affairs. Syracuse University, 1967.

²Lugard, F. D. (1922). *The Dual Mandate in British Tropical Africa* (Edinburgh, 1922), p. 5.

³Hawkins, E. K. (1995). *Road transport in Nigeria: a study of African enterprise*. Routledge, 1958.

⁴ It is important to note that for much of the early part of the 20th Century, Diesel was the main source of fuel. Yet, Diesel is also a petroleum product.

exclusive use by *colonial overlords* was powered by petrol. The colonial authorities relied on imported petrol to power their activities during the colonial era as a result of the near-total dependence on petrol.

Although petrol was an essential commodity needed for the general administration of the Nigerian colony, the “oil majors” who pioneered the building of filling stations across Nigeria left the marketing and distribution of petrol entirely in their hands^{5,6} For instance, as early as 1907, Socony-Vacuum (the face of US-registered Mobil in Nigeria at the time) in conjunction with British Petroleum (BP), is on record as the first marketers of petroleum products in Nigeria in the first decade of the 20th Century.⁷ Similarly, *Compagnie Francaise de L’Afrique Occidentale* (then partners of Texaco) later joined the business of selling petrol in the second decade of the 20th Century.⁸ However, by the fourth year of Nigeria’s independence, Texaco became directly involved in the marketing of petrol through its subsidiary (Texaco Africa).⁹ In the summer of 1927, the Royal Dutch/Shell entered the petrol marketing business in Lagos. Other major players, such as Esso (enlisted in the United States), Agip (registered in Italy), and Elf (registered in France), entered the Nigerian market to sell petrol in 1956, 1962, and 1983, respectively.¹⁰

Downstream Sector after Nigeria’s Political Independence

However, it is important to note that the petroleum products sold in the Nigerian market before 1965 (the year in which the first refinery was built) were imported from outside the country due to the absence of a local refinery.¹¹ According to one estimate, the major oil companies mentioned above established more than “eight dozen filling stations” before 1980.¹² In any case, the spread of filling stations reflected the structure of “colonial infrastructure,”¹³ where the Southern region had more than the North.¹⁴ Aside from the need to locate the filling stations closer to the sea ports in the South, the focus in the South is based on proximity to the market (more car owners in the South than in the North during this period).

With more discoveries of oil in the Middle Eastern region, today’s Niger Delta region, and the commissioning of the first Nigerian refinery in 1965 (through a joint venture agreement between Shell-BP and the Nigerian Federal and Regional Governments), one of the earliest scientists in Nigeria’s oil industry remarked, “the prospects of a fast track to all-round development loomed very large indeed.”¹⁵ However, as a result of the Civil War that raged between 1967 and 1970, Nigeria began to experience petrol shortages.¹⁶ The *Economist Intelligence Unit* (London) reported the effect of the Civil War on both oil production and refining in Nigeria, noting the disruption that accompanied the war in the Eastern and Mid-Western Nigeria that led to petrol scarcity throughout the war’s duration. In fact, a memo from the London Office of BP, which was written to the Nigerian Ministry of Petroleum Resources (then known as the Ministry of Mines and Power), specifically noted that the Port Harcourt refinery was vandalized and later closed between August and mid-1970.¹⁷ As a result, petrol shortages ensued, as soberly

⁵Drabble, Margaret. *The seven sisters*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, 2003.

⁶Either gasoline or petrol stations, the Europeans began building energy stations.

⁷The Government of Nigeria, Colonial Records on Oil sales, National Archive Kaduna, File number 7208.

⁸Ibid. p. 4.

⁹“78 Years of Texaco in Nigeria,” *Guardian* [Lagos], vol. 6, no. 12, 1991.

¹⁰“Nigeria Can Run Refineries Efficiently, Says Abba Gana,” *Guardian* [Lagos] (April 7, 1997).

¹¹The first refinery was built in 1965 through a joint venture agreement between Shell and BP and the Nigerian government.

¹²F. Remilekun, A. Marinho. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, July 10, 2020.

¹³Falola, Toyin. “Britain and Nigeria: exploitation or development?.” (1987).

¹⁴Acemoglu, Daron, Simon Johnson, and James A. Robinson. “The colonial origins of comparative development: An empirical investigation.” *American economic review* 91, no. 5 (2001): 1369-1401.

¹⁵Mohammed Sanusi Barkindo. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 15th July, 2020.

¹⁶Freund, Bill. “Oil boom and crisis in contemporary Nigeria.” *Review of African Political Economy* 5, no. 13 (1978): 91-100.

¹⁷Nigerian Petroleum Refining Co. Ltd.: Business valuation to establish prices to be paid for shares which Government Wish to Acquire,” memo from BP (London) to the Nigerian Ministry of Mines and Power, May 5, 1971, PRO FCO 38/321, 1.

reflected by a pioneer group managing director of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) and reproduced below:

“Although Nigeria’s civil war and thereafter, a petroleum products’ shortage crisis was built, primarily because the Port Harcourt refinery was out of commission and largely because the marketers were unwilling to make capital commitments and cautiously held back from investing in the expansion of infrastructures that were so vitally crucial for coping with the exponentially growing products’ demand.”¹⁸

This study does not focus on the political economy of the war; after all, many academic researchers have almost exhausted the link between oil (as a causal factor) and the Nigerian Civil War.¹⁹ It is important to note that the latter part of this chapter benefited from studies by Paul Collier,²⁰ Michael Ross,²¹ Cyril Obi,²² and Kenneth Omeje,²³ all of whom attempted to study the conflicts in the Niger Delta. However, before establishing the connection between conflicts and petrol shortages, the following will specifically look at the rise of indigenous entrepreneurs in the downstream sector and how these indigenous actors created unhealthy conditions that further worsen the problem of petrol scarcity in Nigeria.

Indigenization Policy in the Downstream Sector

Right into the 1970s, the marketing (downstream sector) of petroleum products, including its production (upstream sector), was essentially dominated by transnational corporations, which, according to conservative estimates, stood at approximately “eighty million tons.”²⁴ To checkmate the overwhelming dominance of the sector by foreign companies, Dr R. B Dikko, the Federal Commissioner of Mines and Power (equivalent to today’s Minister of Petroleum Resources), advocated for greater participation of Nigerians in the sector. He argued that it was necessary for the government “to mitigate the paradox of seemingly less indigenous control and economic independence in a situation of increasing national prosperity.”²⁵ The statement attributed to Dr. Dikko unequivocally shows the government’s preference for indigenous entrepreneurs to participate in the oil sector, especially with increasing revenue gains being recorded. However, the government was also aware of the indigenous actors’ “technical deficiency.”²⁶ Two sources have noted the challenge of technical know-how, which was the only way to ensure the integration of Nigerians (indigenous actors) into the downstream sector. First, Mohammed contended that “most Nigerians remained ignorant about the complexities of oil exploration, extraction, and its marketing despite the inescapable significance of oil to the country’s economy.”²⁷ Second, an opinion piece published in the *Nigerian Tribune* on June 27, 1972, noted the need for the government to prioritize the training of indigenous entrepreneurs to enable them to compete with their foreign counterparts.²⁸

¹⁸Marinho, F. R. A. (2008). *Nigeria’s Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. Macmillan Nigeria Publishers Limited, Lagos, 2008. p. 290.

¹⁹Uche, Chibuike. "Oil, British interests and the Nigerian civil war." *The Journal of African History* 49, no. 1 (2008): 111-135; Uche, Chibuike. "Oil, British interests and the Nigerian civil war." *The Journal of African History* 49, no. 1 (2008): 111-135.

²⁰Collier, Paul. "Natural resources, development and conflict: Channels of causation and policy interventions." *World Bank* 28 (2003).

²¹Ross, Michael. "A closer look at oil, diamonds, and civil war." *Annu. Rev. Polit. Sci* 9 (2006): 265-300

²²Obi, Cyril. "Nigeria’s Niger Delta: Understanding the complex drivers of violent oil-related conflict." *Africa Development* 34, no. 2 (2009).

²³Omeje, Kenneth. *High stakes and stakeholders: Nigeria’s oil conflict and security* Routledge, 2017.

²⁴Genova, Ann. "Oil and nationalism in Nigeria, 1970-1980." PhD insult. 2007.

²⁵Dr. R.B. Dikko-reported in *Nigeria Today* (London) in October 1971.

²⁶Lack of obvious local capacity.

²⁷ Mohammed, Ismaila. "The Nigerian Enterprises Promotion Decrees (1972 and 1977) and Indigenization in Nigeria." PhD diss., University of Warwick, 1985. P. 88.

²⁸“Manpower Training in the Oil Industry in Nigeria,” *Nigerian Tribune* [Ibadan] (June 27, 1972), 4.

In fact, the Gowon regime expressed a desire to train indigenous actors in relevant fields (especially petroleum engineering) with a focus on the downstream sector.²⁹ The marketing of petroleum products does not require much technical training, at least not to the extent of the upstream sector. However, refining petrol, which is within the downstream sector, requires serious technical training as much as the upstream sector. The transnational marketing firms offered training opportunities for interested indigenes after the Nigerian civil war, as reported in the *Daily Times*.³⁰ The Federal Government began to involve indigenes in training as a measure to ensure technology transfer through the creation of the first indigenous Petroleum Training Institute that started operation in 1975. It also made funds available to support students whose research was geared toward petroleum engineering or related aspects of technology, as contended in the government's press release of September 14, 1973, and the *Daily Times* issue of September 8, 1979.

The Nigerian Petroleum Refining Company (a joint venture company that pioneered refining in Nigeria) felt the impact of the indigenization program. After Nigeria increased its shareholding to 50%, the staff composition of expatriate workers had reduced to only 48 compared to the indigenous staff strength of 400.³¹ In fact, the number of expatriate employees further decreased to 26 at the end of 1972. In the same period, the company had its first Nigerian chairman of the management board, leading some observers to conclude that Nigerians made the key strategic decisions.³² However, the Nigerian government criticized foreign companies that appoint Nigerians in ceremonial positions while reserving managerial powers to foreign nationals. Worse still, the government was critical of foreign companies in the oil sector that pressured indigenous staff to offer "voluntary resignation."³³ In the end, regardless of the challenge of the indigenization program, one essential fact is that the military government showed greater interest in taking over ownership of the downstream sector and other sectors of the Nigerian economy. Our focus in the following sub-theme is to explain the evolution of independent marketers and how this class of businessmen/women further entrenched corruption in the sector leading to petrol shortages.

Emergence of Indigenous and Independent Oil Marketers

As part of the government's strategy to increase domestic participation in Nigeria's economic activities, the Military Government of General Yakubu Gowon initiated the *Second National Development Plan*, which covered the period from 1970 to 1974.³⁴ To ensure effective implementation, the Federal Government promulgated the *Nigerian Enterprises Promotion Decree*, which took effect in 1972. However, because British Petroleum (BP) had witnessed the passage of a similar legislation in Guinea (with a focus on the downstream sector), they perceived such a program as antithetical to their interests.³⁵ Notwithstanding the position of BP, the regime showed determination to challenge foreign dominance in some selected economic activities and to protect and secure business spheres for "Nigerians and to ban foreign firms," especially companies that had more than £200,000 in investments.³⁶ While the *First Schedule* of the development plan authorized Nigerians to take full control of businesses in which they have sufficient skills,³⁷ the *Second Schedule* appropriated 40 per cent shares

²⁹ Zakariya, Hasan S. "Transfer of technology under petroleum development contracts." *Journal of World Trade* 16, no. 3 (1982): 207-222.

³⁰Federal Ministry of Information, "Press Release –Petroleum Development Fund Awards Scholarship," [Remark 1] 14 September 1973; Yemi Abimbowe, "The Oil Industry and Manpower," *Daily Times* [Lagos] (8 September 1979), 8.

³¹*Daily Times* Opinion –Realistic!, *Daily Times* [Lagos], May 8, 1972, 3.

³² Austin Osunde, "Oil Industry Given a Boost," *Business Times* [Lagos] (12 October 1976), 8.

³³"Sacking of Nigerians in Oil Firms Halted By Govt," *Daily Times* [Lagos] (8 March 1972),

³⁴Nigeria's Second National Development Plan 1970-74, National Archive Kaduna, Federal Government Files 2312, 1969.

³⁵Unauthored memo, June 30, 1970, BP 8377.

³⁶C.S. Pickard, "indigenization: The Nigerian Enterprises Promotion Decree," PRO, 19 February 1972.

BT 24/2558, 1.

³⁷Obasanjo, O. (1976). "Nigeria on the Forward March," speech, 29 June 1976, in *Embassy of Nigeria, Federal Nigeria Vol. 1, no. 1* (Washington, DC: Embassy of Nigeria, 1976), 2-3.

to Nigerians.³⁸ From the prescription above, activities in the downstream sector were covered in the plan's second schedule.

However, the huge capital requirement set aside as a prerequisite for participation became a serious challenge for the local actors.³⁹ Both Nnoli⁴⁰ and the *New Nigerian Newspaper*⁴¹ observed that local Igbo entrepreneurs who were interested but lacked the required capital protested what they felt was an "exclusionary policy."⁴² The flaws became obvious by the discouraging outcomes and unnecessary delay in the implementation of the plan, as reported in the October 25 issue of *West Africa*, 1982.

Perhaps, this explains why, immediately after the dethronement of Gowon, the Murtala/Obasanjo regime introduced tougher measures aimed at taking over activities in the downstream sector of the Nigerian oil industry from foreign corporations.⁴³ To this effect, the new regime initiated two additional programs, namely, the *Third National Development Plan 1975-1980* and an amended *Nigerian Enterprises Promotion Decree*. The terms of the *Third National Development Plan* were couched to promote more robust domestic participation:

"For the sake of national security, national investment decisions, and managerial opportunities to enable Nigerians to take effective control of the oil industry, the government's direct involvement in the oil industry has become mandatory." To this end, the government will participate in the three phases of the oil industry during the plan period, namely, exploration, refining, and distribution. A National Oil Corporation, together with an associated publicly quoted company, will be established for this purpose.⁴⁴

In line with the observation made above, the military government of General Yakubu Gowon bowed to the dual pressures exerted by domestic nationalist forces on the one hand and the urge to conform to the requirements of the OPEC, promulgated Decree no. 18 of 1971. The Decree, specifically, came into force on April 1, 1971, and established Nigeria's premier holding company (Nigeria National Oil Company), tasked with overseeing Nigeria's oil industry. The decree stated that the organization was to ensure the country "participate in all aspects of petroleum, including exploration, production, refining, marketing, transportation, and distribution."⁴⁵

In addition, the new agency was given the powers to train the indigenous workforce, conduct regular inspections, and supervise pipelines to ensure an adequate supply of petroleum for domestic consumption through the proper organization of the Port-Harcourt refinery and any other matters relating to the organization of allied industries. As would be expected, virtually all the major newspapers in the country expressed great hope and optimism in the establishment of the agency.⁴⁶ However, whether these ambitious objectives were realized is another matter altogether.

Notwithstanding, the corporation immediately swung into action after a series of negotiations that resulted in the execution of Joint Operating Agreements (JOAs) with international oil companies. First, it secured approximately 33.33% and another 35% share interest with Nigerian Agip Oil Company and Safrap (a branch of Elf in Nigeria), respectively. Under this arrangement, the OICs are, by law, the known operator of the stake, while the NNOC operates the licensed area. In furtherance of its pursuit of a greater share of participation in domestic oil dealings and to encourage the NNOC, the Federal Government released an official notice, specifically Government Notice

³⁸Sunday Concord, December 2, 1984

³⁹Dr. R.B. Dikko-reported in *Nigeria Today* (London) October 1971

⁴⁰Okwudiba Nnoli, *Ethnicity and development in Nigeria*. Aldershot: Avebury, 1995. p. 142.

⁴¹*New Nigerian* 15/8/79.

⁴²Count Lamsdorff-in *West Africa* 25/10/82, p. 2,766.

⁴³ Egbule, Philip Onyekachukwu. "Appraising the role of military governments toward nation building in Africa: a focus on Murtala-Obasanjo administration in Nigeria." *Journal of Nation-building & Policy Studies* 3, no. 1 (2019): 103-115.

⁴⁴Federal Government of Nigeria, "Third National Development Plan, 1970-1974," (Lagos: Federal Ministry of Information, 1970).

⁴⁵Part 1, Section 5 (a) of Decree No. 18 of 1971.

⁴⁶*The New Nigeria*, April 2, 1971; *the Punch Newspaper*, June 10, 1971.

No. 311, on February 24, 1972, granting the NNOC the authorization to undertake exploration and production of petroleum resources in all parts of Nigeria, apart from areas that may have been covered by previous licenses.⁴⁷ In furtherance of Nigeria's participation program under NEP, which mandated the retention of a minimum of 60% equity stake in all investing companies within its territory, the Nigerian government secured shares in the oil majors (Gulf, Mobile, and Shell-BP) in 1973, precisely on the 1st of April 1973 (the second year of the establishment of NNOC).⁴⁸ Additionally, it obtained a 60% shareholding in the first refinery and subsequently changed its name to "the Nigeria Petroleum Refining Company (NPRC)" in 1972."⁴⁹ Though the government obtained the required 60% shares, the refinery maintained its identity as a private joint venture company. Consequently, the introduction of indigenous actors into oil marketing as a result of the abovementioned measures culminated in the creation of a new class of "middlemen" known today as "independent marketers" by 1978.⁵⁰ It soon became an attractive venture as the number of those who were attracted soared from less than 10 in 1980 to over 1000 by beginning 1993.⁵¹ A close review of official records indicates an overwhelming increase in the number of independent marketers in 2010, which stood at over 7,500.⁵² With the emergence of local actors in the downstream sector, especially in the marketing of oil products, one would expect improvement in the sector's performance. However, it seems that the introduction of local actors only birthed a class of new exploiters as the activities in the downstream sector continue to deteriorate with the persistent scarcity of fuel as a constant feature of the Nigerian economy.⁵³ The new business class, otherwise known as middlemen (oil marketers) "continue to grow not only in size but also in influence."⁵⁴ Sometimes, they used labor union platforms to "pressure the government on their selfish demands that would benefit their members while adding to the already precarious economic condition of the 1980s."⁵⁵

However, a closer review of the implementation of indigenization policy in the Nigerian downstream sector would reveal glaring contradictions as "state officials and their cronies in business became the major beneficiaries of whatever good intentions the policy was meant to generate." The privileged class that constitutes a minute percentage of Nigeria's population became the major beneficiaries in the quest to enhance what Schwarz described as "nurturing capitalism."⁵⁶ Adejugbe observed how the shares in the newly acquired companies were unevenly sold, a practice that led to the concentration of shares in the hands of a few individuals.⁵⁷ Even Mr. G.A. Akamiokho (Chief Executive Officer of the Nigeria Securities and Exchange Commission) accused the Lagos Stock Exchange of engaging in favoritism rather than providing a fair and plain level ground for investors,

⁴⁷Government Notice No. 311 of 1972 can be found in the Federal Government Files located in the Ministry of Information Archive in Kaduna, specifically file no. 7123/FG.

⁴⁸Shehu M. Yar'Adua was the Nigerian chief of Staff, Supreme Headquarters During the Obasanjo regime. Addressing the members of the then vibrant Management Institute of Nigeria (MIN), he announced that the "Government was going to embark on creeping Nationalization", September 1976.

⁴⁹NPRC Company Reports, 1972.

⁵⁰National Daily March 18, 1978. Pp. 36-37.

⁵¹Ehinomen, Christopher, and Adepoju Adeleke. "An assessment of the distribution of petroleum products in Nigeria." *E3 Journal of Business Management and Economics* 3, no. 6 (2012): 232-241.

⁵²The PPPRA records show that the number of independent marketers exceeded 7000 by 2010.

⁵³Nkem Agetua, "NNPC Renews Contract with Oil Marketers," Friday, May 13, 1983, p. 1.

⁵⁴Suleiman, Lookman. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 12th July, 2020.

⁵⁵ Akpoghomeh, Osi S., and Dele Badejo. "Petroleum product scarcity: a review of the supply and distribution of petroleum products in Nigeria." *OPEC review* 30, no. 1 (2006): 27-40.

⁵⁶Schatz, Sayre P. *Nigerian capitalism*. University of California Press, 1977. p. 2.

⁵⁷Adejugbe, Michael. "The myths and realities of Nigeria's business indigenization." *Development and Change* 15, no. 4 (1984): 577-592. Pp. 582-583

including those in the downstream sector of Nigeria's petroleum industry.⁵⁸ Although there is no sufficient data to support this claim, Mr. G.A. Akamiokho was an insider who provided a clear indication of some wrong doings. However, at a general level, the Industrial Panel report (1976) corroborated the speculation of inappropriate practices.⁵⁹

This can be seen from a major revelation published in the *New Nigerian* newspaper of 1983 entitled "Ugly Nigerians," which quoted Mr. Minso Gadzama, who was then the Chairperson of NEPD, verbatim:

"Many Nigerians participate in tearing apart the fabric and have hastened the collapse of our economy. Regrettably, they are the ones who shout the loudest about our so-called lack of leadership in the management of the economy. Yet they are the same people who are in the lead in contravening the laws designed to create prosperity and progress for the people of this country."⁶⁰

This remark, if anything, served as a glaring indictment of the local entrepreneurs, including those within the Nigerian downstream sector, who have been integrated following indigenization policy.

Conclusion

Drawing from the above explanation, there is a basis to argue that the activities of oil marketers have contributed, in no small measure, to the menace of Nigeria's petrol shortages. This study traced the evolution of these entrepreneurial classes to the 1970s and argued that their introduction to the sector, which was within the framework of the Nigerian government's indigenization program, may not have resolved the challenge of petrol shortages. Rather than serving the Nigerian economy with patriotism, the oil marketers operate without patriotism. This article explored the organic evolution and development of the downstream sector of Nigeria's petroleum industry.

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⁵⁸West Africa (London), 16/6/1972, p. 777.

⁵⁹Hoogvelt, Ankie. "Indigenization and foreign capital: industrialization in Nigeria." *Review of African Political Economy* 6, no. 14 (1979): 56-68.

⁶⁰The Editorial "Ugly Nigerians" *New Nigerian Newspaper* of 27 July 1983. pp. 23-24.

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